

Acta Futura 12 (2020) 133-149

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3747356

**Acta
Futura**

Considerations on Life Support Systems for Interstellar Travel: a Regenerative Story

VOLPONI, M.* AND LASSEUR, C.

DIRECTORATE OF TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING AND QUALITY (TEC), ESA
ESTEC, KEPLERLAAN 1, 2200AG NOORDWIJK, THE NETHERLANDS

Abstract. Humanity has always been fascinated by stars, from the mythological explanations of the dawn of civilizations to the most modern astrophysics theories. In the last 50 years we have understood (and proven) that we are able to live and travel outside Earth, and while we are planning to slowly exploring our Solar System, settling on the Moon, on Mars and on various space stations, the idea of reaching other star systems is more and more widespread. However, the limits of Einstein's General Relativity seem to withstand even every possible future physics discovery, so we probably have to accept that we will never be able to go faster than the speed of light and that, ultimately, interstellar travel will fundamentally be a matter of patience. Even going to the closest star systems will take more than one century, so spaceships capable of sustaining the lives of tens of thousands of individuals are the only viable option to perform such a travel. With this in mind, it is immediately clear that the production and the recycling of the resources (i.e. food, water and oxygen) on board the spaceship is of foremost importance, and it has to be done at such a level of perfection that, basically, every spacecraft shall function as a miniature Earth. In this article, the present state of the art of life support systems for space missions is outlined, giving an insight of the actual systems running on the International Space Station and their capabilities to maintain the astronauts alive, regenerating water and air, as well as minimising the risk for chemical and microbiological contamination: for every relevant system, an explanation of the working principle is given, highlighting the achievements as well as the current limitations. Starting from their planned upgrades, the present and future lines of research are discussed, encompassing physical, chemical and biological regeneration systems studies. The effectiveness of current life support is reviewed against the possible future systems, some already in development, and the different levels of closure achievable are discussed, together with their usefulness in different mission scenarios. At the end, a broader view of a possible spaceship is sketched, with issues comprising psychological wellness, social structure and interactions, radiation hazard, components and materials productions, to try to give an omni-comprehensive picture on how huge the challenge is to explore the universe outside the Solar System.

1 Introduction

Humanity has always been fascinated by stars. At the dawn of civilization, men had hypothesised these brilliant spots to be gods, holes in the sky were the light

of the infinite was filtering, or bowls of fire attached to the ultimate shell of the universe. The fantasies of men were using them and myths and constellations arose. But the birth of science and the extensive study of the sky have slowly revealed stars as objects similar to our Sun, each one with possibly multiple planets revolving,

*Corresponding author. E-mail: marco.volponi@esa.int

all scattered across the vastness of the universe: from there, the thirst of exploration grew to new and inconceivable levels, and the desire of reaching these other suns manifested. Artists and writers were the first to try to satisfy this desire, imagining adventurous voyages to the other planets of our and other solar systems, with often encounters with other civilizations and arising in the popular culture the concept of space travel. However, what about actually realising it?

Space travel is still in its very beginning: in fact, the furthest distance a human has travelled is the Moon (which is about 384 000 km, or 1.3 light-second), and a date for the first interplanetary travel (Mars) is still unclear and will probably not happen before the next 10-20 years. The actual main problems that prevent going to Mars are the protection of the crew (but also the hardware of the space ship) from the radiations and the mass of the resources. In fact, every human consumes every day roughly 1 kg of oxygen, 1 kg of food and 3 kg of water [1], and the current state of regeneration on board of the ISS is around 50% for oxygen, 90% for water and nothing for the food. With these numbers, for a 1 000-days round-trip to Mars, the mass needed to be transported for the survival of every astronaut is around 2 tons! Moreover, if we want to include in this figure also the water and the consumables needed for the crew hygiene, the value immediately goes up by a factor of 2 or 3. This makes manifest that a huge effort has to be put forward in order to enhance dramatically the recycling capabilities of future space ship, both improving the current technologies and developing novel ones.

2 Current State of the Art

Presently, NASA states that on the International Space Station (ISS), 90% of the water is recycled, together with 42% of the oxygen recovered from the CO₂ [2]. This is done via a combination of systems, both American, Russian and, recently, European.

Let us start examining the systems in the USA portion of the ISS. There the Air Revitalization System is mainly composed of four parts: the Carbon Dioxide Removal Assembly (CDRA, left panel of Figure 1), the Oxygen Generation Assembly (OGA), the CO₂ Reduction Assembly (CReA) and the Trace Contaminants Control System (TCCS).

The CDRA main function is to extract the CO₂ in excess from the cabin air and either vent it to space or feed

it to the CReA: it works using the property of zeolites, which are microporous aluminosilicate minerals, of adsorbing molecules in their cavities at low temperatures and releasing them when heated up. Since water (air humidity) is more readily adsorbed than CO₂, a double stage approach is used: a first molecular sieve strips humidity from the air, while the second effectively eliminates the carbon dioxide. In order not to lose any water and to ensure continuous operation, alternatively two different pairs of adsorbent bed, two in adsorption mode and two in desorption mode, are used, as can be seen in Figure 2. The advantage of this system is that only a little amount of consumables is used: in fact, the zeolites are in turn regenerated and only a small amount of oxygen, nitrogen and water are lost during the venting phase.

The Oxygen Generation Assembly (OGA) uses electrical energy to exploit the electrolysis of water in order to produce oxygen and hydrogen: the first is directed towards the inside of the station, while the hydrogen is split between the CReA and the venting port. It is sized so that, if run in continuous mode, it can provide the oxygen for 8.25 humans (which is the amount to sustain seven astronauts plus the eventual biological specimens (e.g. mice) and the atmospheric losses).

These two systems, taken alone, do not recycle anything: they simply maintain the atmosphere composition constant by removing carbon dioxide and injecting oxygen¹. In order to increase the closure of the system, the CReA was developed. Its principle of operation is based on the Sabatier reaction, which was discovered in 1897 by the French chemist Paul Sabatier (subsequently awarded the Nobel Prize for this finding): at temperatures between 300° and 400° C and elevated pressures, in the presence of a catalyst like nickel, carbon dioxide and hydrogen combines together to form water and methane. With this reaction part of the carbon dioxide and hydrogen generated as wastes from the OGA and the CDRA (which would otherwise be vented into space) are combined to form water and methane: the second is still lost (in space, as always), but the water contributes again to the needs of the Station. The combination of these three systems perform a partial closure of the oxygen cycle (around 40%, according to NASA [2]), but carbon and part of the hydrogen are still squandered from the spacecraft.

¹There is also another problem, which is the nitrogen lost in all this processes and in the leaks: currently there is no other method on board of restoring it if not through the appropriate storage tank, which is resupplied from Earth.

FIGURE 1. Left, the CDRA; right, three Elektron modules (courtesy of NASA).

FIGURE 2. (a) During the first cycle, the air (properly filtered to avoid particles to enter in the air revitalization loop) pass through the desiccant bed A, which strips the humidity carried, before entering the CO₂ sorbent bed D, which traps the carbon dioxide. Before re-entering into the cabin, the dry, low-carbon air pass to the desiccant bed B, which is desorbing the humidity trapped in the previous cycle. In the meantime, the CO₂ sorbent bed C is heated up, releasing the gas that is vented into space or fed to the CReA. (b) During the second cycle, the functions of the various bed are inverted, so as the air flux: the humidity is now trapped in the (empty) bed B while it is released from the (full) bed A; same for the bed C and D.

Aside from the CO₂ removal and the O₂ replenishment, it is very important to keep the amount of contaminants in the air below the thresholds agreed as non-toxic [3] and non-pathogenic [4]: while this is something that can sound strange at first, we have

to think that in space you cannot “open the window and refresh the air”! There are many sources of unwanted molecules in the ISS atmosphere: for example, the offgassing from materials (especially plastics), the metabolic by-products, the smell caused by food and

its preparation processes, the housekeeping cleaners, all the scientific experiments, etc. All these molecules are continuously produced and so the necessity of removing them consistently arise: the Trace Gas Contamination Control is there exactly to perform this task. It is composed of three elements: first, a charcoal bed (impregnated with phosphoric acid) removes the high-molecular weight compounds and ammonia; then, a catalytic oxidiser use high temperature (400° - 500° C) and a palladium-on-alumina catalyst to oxidise CO, CH₄, H₂ and other low molecular weight compounds that are not adsorbed mainly into CO₂ and H₂O; finally, a sorbent bed made of lithium hydroxide (LiOH) adsorbs the acid by-products of the catalytic oxidation (such as HCl, Cl₂, F₂, NO₂, SO₂). All these systems together manage to keep the atmosphere composition into safe limits, but they are bulky, energy hungry and still require a good amount of consumables.

As long as water is regarded, the American section is equipped with a system spanning two racks, called Water Recovery System 1 and 2. They consists of a Urine Processor Assembly (UPA), which transform urine into brine and distilled water, which is further fed to the Water Processor Assembly (WPA), together with the air condensate and the other wastewaters, which turns water potable again.

The UPA basically use a Distillation Assembly to recover 85% of the water content of the urine² (which is pre-treated with flush water, an oxidant - chromium trioxide -, and an inorganic acid - phosphoric acid - to control microbial growth and inhibit precipitation): it consists of a rotating centrifuge, where the waste urine stream is evaporated at low pressure, compressed, and subsequently condensed on the opposite side of the evaporator surface to conserve latent energy. Waste brine is stored in a special tank and properly disposed, while the produced water is fed to the WPA, mixed with the other wastewaters.

The WPA, at first, employs a series of filters to takes away particles, inorganic and non-volatile molecules

²Actually, the UPA was initially designed and tested to achieve 85% recovery of the water. Unexpectedly, tests on the ISS resulted in precipitation of calcium sulphate due to the higher amount of calcium in the astronauts' urine (due to the augmented bone loss in microgravity), so the performance had to be lowered to 70% [5]. However, after years of study, it was understood that the problem was in the pre-treatment: changing the acid used from sulphuric to phosphoric made possible to increase the concentration of calcium in the discarded brine, restoring the original capacity of UPA. Test actually suggested that, with this novel pre-treatment, it would be even possible to go up to 90% recovery [6].

from the stream. Subsequently, the water passes through a catalytic reactor, where low molecular weight organics not removed by the adsorption process are oxidized in the presence of oxygen, elevated temperature and a catalyst. A gas separator removes the excess oxygen and the gaseous by-products, while the water, after being checked by the Reactor Health Sensor for quality (based on the electrical conductivity), passes through an ion exchange bed, which removes dissolved products of oxidation and adds iodine for residual microbial control. Following that, the water is subsequently stored in the product water tank prior to delivery to the ISS potable water bus.

The Russian segment of the ISS has also its own life support system, which is combined together with the American one just described to ensure stability, redundancy and efficiency of the space station.

The Elektron system, shown in right panel of Figure 1, is an oxygen-generating device, inherited from the Mir systems. Like the American OGA, it uses water electrolysis to split water molecules into gaseous oxygen and hydrogen, which is vented into space. Three units are currently installed aboard the ISS. Another method to provide oxygen, developed by Roscosmos, is the Vika Solid-Fuel Oxygen Generator (SFOG), which burns cartridges (or "candles") of lithium perchlorate and iron: each candle provides the amount of O₂ needed for one person for 24 h. Clearly, it is a non-regenerative system, and it is only used as a backup system, in case the other nominal system experience a failure.

For CO₂ removal, a system operating on the same principle of the CDRA is also present in the Russian segment of the station: called Vozdukh, it operates using three bed instead of four, and it also uses a regenerable solid sorbent [7]. Both the American and the Russian systems were needed when the crew of the Space Shuttle mission was visiting the ISS: for brief periods, the station was inhabited by 13 astronauts!

Regarding water recovery, the Zvezda module has a system for removing water vapour from the atmosphere and transforming it to water to be fed to the Elektron to produce oxygen (but can also be drank). The urine collected in the Russian toilet is harvested and can be manually fed to the American Urine Processor Assembly.

A new European system has recently been installed (October 2018) on the ISS and it is undergoing tests before starting operation: it is called LSR, or Life Support Rack (previously known as ACLS, or Advanced Close Loop System) [8, 9], and it comprises in a stan-

FIGURE 3. Left, Veggie, and right, APH, on the ISS (courtesy of NASA).

standard payload rack all the functions of the American ARS. The assembly traps carbon dioxide from the air as it passes through small beds made from a unique amine (developed by Airbus DS, together with ESA) for human spaceflight. Steam is then used to extract the carbon dioxide and process it in a Sabatier reactor to create methane and water. Electrolysis then splits the water back into oxygen while the methane is vented into space. LSR is designed to provide air revitalisation functions for a crew of 3 persons, but the challenges to achieve these numbers still remains enormous.

Food production has not been mentioned because the advancements towards it have been very slow in the past years. It is true that, compared to the recycling of water and oxygen, food production requires more volume, mass and energy, and a large implementation (i.e. for more than 20% of the astronauts' diet mass) of it pays off only for very long duration and/or very distant space missions (typical figure is bigger than twenty years near Earth and various years permanence on Mars [10]); this is obviously not true for precursors and small size implementations. Some small step in that direction have been undertaken by NASA first with the Vegetable Production System (better known as Veggie, left panel of Figure 3) [11, 12] and afterwards with the Advance Plant Habitat (APH, right panel of Figure 3) [13]. While Veggie was more a test bed of the actual ability of growing safely edible plants in space, APH is already meant to be a growth chamber for scientific purposes with a high grade of automation, in order to reduce heavily the crew-time needed to run it. In parallel, ESA is developing a growth chamber, to be fit inside and European Drawer Rack (EDR), able to cultivate potatoes in space,

called Precursor of Food Production Unit (PFPU): this modular system is envisaged to be progressively flown and tested in the following years, and to become operative around 2024 [14].

However, the ISS is not the only place where horticultural space technologies are studied: another good example is Eu:CROPIS (Euglena and Combined Regenerative Organic-Food Production in Space) [15], a satellite built by the German Aerospace Centre (Deutsches Zentrum für Luft und- Raumfahrt, or DLR). This satellite exploits the ability of certain bacteria to transform synthetic urine into fertilizer for the greenhouse, where tomatoes are planned to be grown, and for the *Euglena gracilis*, which is a photosynthetic algae. The axial rotational motion of the satellite will simulate the gravity condition of the Moon first and Mars afterwards: the data collected will help to understand better how a greenhouse on these celestial bodies would behave.

3 Future Development

As stated at the beginning of the previous section, the present rate of closure of the onboard systems of the Space Station is low and incomplete, so multiple studies and projects all over the world are ongoing to raise the level and the reliability of recycling.

NASA is currently studying a way to further extract water from the urine brine: after ground testing multiple systems, the choice went on the Brine Processor Assembly [16]. Its principle of operation is based on membrane distillation: an ionomer-microporous membrane pair contains the brine while transferring puri-

FIGURE 4. *The rendering of the planned Deep Space Gateway (courtesy of NASA).*

fied water vapour to the cabin air, transported tangentially via forced convection. On-ground breadboard tests have achieved a total water loop closure of 98%, which is in line with what is required by NASA for future human exploration in its Water Recovery Technology Roadmap. A test unit will be flown on the ISS in the next years.

Both ESA and NASA are also further investigating methods to close the hydrogen loop in the air revitalization system by further splitting the methane produced by the Sabatier reactor. Up to now, different reaction have been taken into account and tested; one, for example, is the methane pyrolysis: at 1200° C, methane splits into inorganic carbon and H₂, which, if successful, could be fed again into the Sabatier reactor and so close the hydrogen loop. NASA is looking into this, but precisely at the incomplete reaction that takes place at lower temperatures, and splits methane into gaseous hydrogen and acetylene (C₂H₂): this can be achieved by creating a methane plasma bombarding the gas with microwaves [17]. Another option, also investigated by NASA, is using the Bosch reaction [18]: this is a two-step mechanism to convert CO₂ and hydrogen to water and solid carbon. In the first step, CO₂ reacts with hydrogen in the Reverse Water-Gas Shift reaction to form carbon monoxide (CO) and water; in the second step, the carbon monoxide is further reduced to

solid, elemental carbon by either hydrogenation (CO + H₂ → H₂O + C_{solid}), or by self-disproportionation in the Boudouard reaction (2 CO → CO₂ + C_{solid}). The Bosch reaction could theoretically provide 100% recovery of the hydrogen in the methane generated from the Sabatier, but the solid carbon deposition makes it challenging to engineer. Actually, none of the technology developed and tested has demonstrated efficiencies high enough to consider these systems a viable option towards methane recovery.

JAXA, on the other hand, is trying to develop in parallel a complete air and water revitalization system, using technologies analogue to what discussed before. The idea is to use the ISS as a benchmark test for their systems in order to be ready to build a part of the life support system of the Deep Space Gateway [19] (Figure 4).

As long as removing trace gas contaminants is regarded, a very promising new technology is photocatalysis: photons (mostly in the UV range) are irradiated onto a TiO₂ catalyst that, splitting the air humidity into hydroxyl radicals (OH) and oxide ions (O₂⁻), deal a lot of diverse functions, from decompositions of contaminants, deodorisation, anti-bacteria action and self-cleaning [20].

On the food production side, a recent ongoing important experiment is EDEN-ISS [21]. Lead by DLR, a big

consortium of industrial and academic partners has built a greenhouse at the Neumayer Station III, in Antarctica, with the aim of advancing the knowledge of managing the growth of plants in extreme, highly isolated environment, and the ultimate goal of better understanding how a greenhouse on the Moon or on Mars can be designed. A small portion of it was dedicated to RUCOLA (Rack-like Unit for Consistent on-orbit Leafy crops Availability) [22], a rack-like facility designed as an International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR), which was testing technologies for a weightlessness autonomous cultivation system.

Another approach to resources recycling is adopted by the closed ecological systems: these are meant to be ecosystems with a complete level of closure, where ideally only power and heat rejection are necessary as an exchange with the outside. These systems envisage the use of some biological species in the loop (apart from the human crew, clearly), where the wastes of a species are profitably used as nutrients by at least one another species: clearly, to make it completely independent from any contribution of matter from the outside, at least one species has to be autotroph, and often, in fact, algae are inserted into these loop. Notable examples of this kind of life support system are BIOS-3, Biosphere-2, CEEF and the more recent Yuegong-1 ("Lunar Palace 1)."

BIOS-3 [23] was a hermetic room with a volume of 315 m³ built in the Institute of Biophysics in the Krasnoyarsk Academgorodok, in Russia, in 1972. The volume was divided into four compartments, in two of which phytotrons were located, in one a microalgae cultivators, and in the latter - the crew area - consists of three single-cabins, a galley, a lavatory and a control room. During the years, a total of ten experiments were conducted with crews of 1 to 3 people: the longest experiment lasted 180 days (1972-1973). It was possible to achieve a complete closure of the system in gas and water, and up to 80% of the crew's food needs. In the greenhouses, thanks to artificial light, many different plants were grown, like wheat, soybeans, lettuce, carrots, radishes, beets, potatoes, cabbage, onions, and others. All plants were special varieties: for example, dwarf wheat with a shortened stem, bred by Professor G. M. Lisovsky, was used, which made it possible to minimize the volume of inedible biomass and increase the surface yield of the phytotrons.

Biosphere-2 [24], shown in right panel of Figure 5, was one of the biggest and most controversial experiment ever tried in the USA. The name is symbolic:

is modelled after Earth, which stands as biosphere-1. Built in 1991, it consists in a series of different biomes area (rainforest, ocean with coral reef, mangrove wetlands, savannah grassland, fog desert, agricultural area and human habitat), all connected and completely sealed from the outside; it was meant to be a miniature world completely self-sufficient, capable of sustaining the life of 8 "biospherians" indefinitely. The numbers were impressive: it is spanning a total of 12 700 m², 203 000 m³ under sealed glass, 6 500 windows, and during the missions more than 3 800 living species were hosted inside. The success of the two missions were not good as expected and the entire story of the complex has inspired entire books [25, 26, 27]. The first mission lasted two years, but not without internal crew problems, suspects of cheating by inserting food and scrubbing CO₂, all under a massive media coverage. The second mission was actually sabotaged by two members of the first mission, and so the experiments came to an end. In 2011 was took over by the University of Arizona, which uses it as a laboratory for multiple experiments and also as a touristic attraction.

In Japan, in 1995, the Closed Ecological Experiment Facility (CEEF) [28] was realised in the Aomori Prefecture. At the beginning, it was part of the Institute for Environmental Sciences (IES) and it was developed in order to track radioisotopes through closed ecosystems. When not in use for its primary purposes, the facility could be utilized for studies of controlled environment agriculture and human life support: CEEF scientists designed complete diets from crops grown in the 150 m² of the plant cultivation modules, experimenting both with natural sunlight and with High-Pressure Sodium Lamps. Also in these facilities, multiple mission to test human survival were performed, even though of short duration (from 1 to 4 weeks). The crew was eating foods grown inside the facility (major crops were rice, soybean and peanut); in addition to the humans, two miniature goats were enclosed in the system and were fed inedible parts (leaves and stems) of the crops.

In China, recently, bioregenerative support systems has gained a lot of momentum. In the Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics (BUAA), in 2014, the Yuegong-1, or Lunar Palace 1 [29] (left panel of Figure 5), has been built; it is meant to be a precursor study in order to develop knowledge and expertise for a future base on the surface of the Moon. It consist in a self-contained laboratory (the total surface is 160 m² and the volume 500 m³) where the life of 3 humans are supported by the vegetation area. In fact, the totality of

FIGURE 5. Left, a view inside Lunar Palace 1; right, an aerial view of Biosphere-2 (courtesy of Reuters and the University of Arizona).

oxygen and water is claimed to be recycled inside, and only a small portion of consumables is inserted from the outside. The diet is based mainly on vegetables, but in the latest missions, mealworms were farmed, in order to guarantee a higher amount of protein to the crew.

A slightly different approach is constituted by the controlled ecological systems: with these terms are usually indicated those systems that employ both physico-chemical and biological processes in order to recycle the water, air and food, but with a greater degree of control and engineering of the processes themselves. They typically try to minimise at the maximum extent mass, volume and power necessary to perform the loop closure by maximising the efficiency of the single subsystem, both by choosing the most functional one and to exploiting it to its maximum potential.

The NASA Controlled Ecological Life Support System (CELSS) [30] program was started in 1978 by the Life Sciences Division with the assumption that NASA's goals would eventually include extended duration missions with sizeable crews requiring capabilities beyond the ability of conventional life support technology. The CELSS concept was based upon the integration of biological and physico-chemical processes to form a system that would produce food, potable water and a breathable atmosphere from metabolic and other wastes, in a stable and reliable approach. The main characteristic of CELSS was the use of green plant photosynthesis to produce food, with the resulting production of oxygen and potable water, and the removal of carbon dioxide. The project made a lot of advancement in life support science, both on ground and in space, but was gradually slowed down in the nineties and its remaining were integrated into the global life support systems studies as Advanced Life Support Systems (Veggie and APH are two examples of the heritage

of CELSS).

The European programme on controlled ecological system is MELiSSA (Micro Ecological Life Support System Alternative) [31]: this project, supported by ESA, aims to build life support systems for space missions as small as possible, recycling theoretically everything, taking advantage of biological, chemical and physical systems. The system takes inspiration from mountain lake ecosystem: five main processes were identified (one being the consumers), and based on this the idea of the MELiSSA loop was shaped. This loop is built around the crewmembers and other four compartments, which progressively transform the wastes and give them a new life (see Figure 6).

The first compartment is called the Liquefying Compartment: it is the collection point of all the mission wastes, from the human ones to the kitchen ones, including also the non-edible part of plants grown in the IVb compartment and biodegradable packaging; a consortium of bacteria anaerobically digest these elements into ammonium, CO₂, volatile fatty acids and minerals. For biosafety reasons and for optimum degradation efficiency, the compartment operates in thermophilic conditions (55° C). The process of degradation in this compartment is carried out by proteolysis, saccharolysis and cellulolysis. Up to now, the overall biodegradation efficiency by the selected inoculum allows reaching reasonable values (i.e. proteolysis 70%, fibre 44%). Better degradation values are currently limited by two factors: the slow degradation of fibrous material (i.e. cellulose, xylan, and lignin) and the mechanical difficulty of extracting these non-degraded compounds for a specific and more adapted treatment. To improve this degradation level, several technologies are studied (near-critical oxidation, fungi, rumen bacteria, mesophilic anaerobic and hyperthermophilic bacteria, ...).

FIGURE 6. A schematic representation of the MELiSSA loop, with the five compartments and their relations highlighted (courtesy of the MELiSSA Foundation).

The second compartment is the Photoheterotrophic Compartment, where the bacteria *Rhodospirillum Rubrum* is responsible for the elimination of the terminal products of the liquefying compartment (mainly the volatile fatty acids).

The third compartment is called the Nitrifying Compartment: its main function is to transform the nitrogen compounds coming from urine and the outputs of the degradation of the previous reactors into nitrates, which is the most favourable source of nitrogen for the algae and higher plants. To achieve this goal, a consortium of two bacteria is used: first, *Nitrosomonas Europaea* oxidise the ammonia, CH_4^+ , into nitrite ions, NO_2^- ; then, *Nitrobacter Winogradskyi* further oxidise the nitrite into nitrate, NO_3^- , which is a form of nitrogen metabolisable by plants. This two bacteria species live together also in Earth ecosystems, and they are the major player in the nitrification part of the nitrogen cycle of the planet. Note that these reactions require oxygen

to be performed: this will be produced by the IVa&b compartment, together with the quantity needed to sustain the crew. In this compartment the hydrodynamics is crucial: in fact, it is a fixed bed reactor, so the coexistence of a solid, a liquid and a gaseous part has to be managed, which in space is even more complicated.

The Photoautotrophic Compartment is divided in two sections: the C IVa, or the “algae compartment”, and the C IVb, or the Higher Plants Compartment. In the first, a bioreactor hosts a cyanobacteria, *Limnospira Indica*³, commonly known as Spirulina: while nowadays is being sold as a miraculous superfood in western countries, it has been used as an everyday food since remote times by some populations of the Mesoamerica [33] and the part of Africa around the Chad Lake [34]. This bacterium has been chosen because of the well-known acceptance for human diet, its high protein content and

³Previously known as *Arthrospira Platensis*: see [32]

the high pH in culture medium, which lowers the risk of contamination from other bacteria strains. In this photobioreactor, the *Spirulina* transforms, through the photosynthesis, the CO₂ coming from the C I and C V the minerals and nitrates from C III into edible mass and oxygen: in the MELiSSA projects, all the stoichiometries have been extensively studied and predictive models have been validated during continuous experiments. On the other hand, The Higher Plants Compartment is crucial because, while also converting carbon dioxide and nitrates into oxygen and food, it produce potable water through the transpiration process. Up to now, eight crops have been considered and tested (wheat, tomato, potato, soybean, rice, spinach, onion, lettuce), but in the future more can be added. The most challenging aspect of this (sub-)compartment is the physico-chemical characterization of the plants and their internal processes: in fact, understanding the biomass production rates, the interdependence of metabolic pathways and reactions on environmental parameters, as well as their mineral and proximate compositions is of foremost importance.

As can be seen, the goal of the MELiSSA project are much more ambitious than the future extensions of the actually used systems: in fact, in this way, not only oxygen and hydrogen loops are closed, but also carbon, nitrogen, sulphur, and other elements. The rate of closure of this kind of system is truly encompassing the totality of the resources: for very long duration missions, like a Moon or planetary base or interstellar travel, this is probably what we should look for.

4 Interstellar Travel

Interstellar travel would be completely another scale of space travel. In fact, the closest star to the Sun is Proxima Centaury, which is about 4.2 ly (light-years) apart, and the centre of the Milky Way is approximately 26 000 ly apart: so the minimum distance for reaching another interesting solar system has to be (at least!) in the order of the tenth of light-years.

Despite all the efforts of going beyond it, after more than one century, Einstein's General Relativity is still in good shape and there are no signs of the possibility of accelerating a massive object faster than the speed of light. Moreover, the existence of dimensions extra to the four of space-time we are all used to is being ruled out pretty strongly with particle experiments (e.g. at CERN); no signs of tunnelling structure across space-time - commonly known as wormholes - has ever been

detected; every theoretical project to warping space-time in order to go faster than light involves the use of "exotic particles" (like particles with imaginary mass, for example), which not only has never been observed, but they also have little room in the current constraints which the Standard Model imposes. So (sadly!), we have to accept the idea the maybe we will be forever bounded by the upper limit of the speed of light, and interstellar travel will be, above all, a matter of patience.

In this case, the travel will have a duration superior to a human life; so, basically, two solutions emerge: sleeping pods and generation ships⁴. The first idea is based on the ability, shown by some animals, of undergoing a long period of deep sleep, called hibernation, where the temperature of the body drops, metabolic functions stay at a minimum and the body remains immobile, while ingesting no food nor water, and the oxygen consumption is kept to a very minimum. The possibility of making humans capable of undergoing such a state have been researched in the past years, mainly with the purpose of slowing down the body functions of a heavily injured person in order to have the time to reach a proper centre capable of intervene and save his/her life. While hours of hibernation seems feasible, and maybe even reachable in the near future, a very long (i.e. years) state of stasis could be unattainable without major damages. But assuming it would be possible to actually restore normal vital parameter of humans after years of stasis inside some "sleeping pods", this method could be used to send a space ship, completely autonomous, with a crew of 150-200⁵ (even if, to have a population with a genetic drift sustainable almost indefinitely, the number appears to be in the order of 10 000 persons [36]) to an another solar system, which would wake them up when they would have arrived to their destination to start setting up a colony on the designated planet⁶. Research in this topic has gained momentum in the last years (see, for example, [37]), and maybe it could be actually achieved in this century to have human undergoing weeks of torpor, interspersed by regular interval of awakening.

Generation ships, an artistic impression of which can

⁴Actually, human imagination has not limited itself only to this two possibilities, but they seem even more speculative than science fiction, so they will not be taken into consideration into this article.

⁵This is the minimum number found to not give interbreeding problems for some generations [35]

⁶In order to decrease the number of colonists, it has been proposed also to bring a certain amount of frozen human embryos, in order to enlarge the genetic population without the need of sustain the gene carrier alive during the travel.

FIGURE 7. *The rendering of the interior of a generation ship (courtesy of Crytek).*

be seen in Figure 7, on the other hand, are the only currently thinkable viable mean of performing an interstellar travel. The idea consists in a huge spaceship, which sustains a population of thousands of individuals for centuries, while marriages, births and death occurs naturally as on Earth, and the population is continuously renewed generation after generation.

In both cases, the necessity of recycling resources is mandatory, due to the size and the duration of the mission. The most challenging situation is clearly the second one, where even a minimal loss of a resource during time could become of huge impact on the mission scale. Let us do a quick calculation. Let us imagine that we will be able to build a spaceship capable of travelling at $0.1 c$, which correspond to $30\,000\text{ km/s}$ (for comparison, Voyager 1 is now leaving the Solar System at a cruising speed of about $62\,000\text{ km/h}$, or $0.00006 c$): then the travel to one of the closest star ($\sim 10\text{ ly}$) would take approximately one century. To have a very high chance of success and guarantee unlimited genetic stability, a crew of at least $10\,000$ persons is envisaged; together with the 5 kg/d/crewmember of consumables, another 10 kg are taken into account for personal hygiene. If we imagine having a system which every day recycle 99.9% of the resources, it still means that, during the travel, a mass of $5\,500$ tons will be lost! Now it is easy to see how minimising losses is of foremost

importance in an interstellar travel.

In addition to these considerations, also the astronauts' diet has to be seriously taken into account. For maximising the efficiency, the diet should be completely vegan, since protein conversion done by animals has an efficiency that is an order of magnitude lower than certain plants; on the other hand, a complete vegan diet has to be properly managed in order not to cause deficiencies. A huge variety of plants species will help mitigating this risk (together with increasing the resistance against possible diseases, which could suddenly kill an entire cultivar), and a proper nutritional and culinary education has to be implemented. For some isolated elements, supplements or fortified foods can be foreseen, like, for example, the vitamin B12, which is completely absent in the vegetal realm, but it can be synthesised by a bacteria culture and harvested.

In general, some small animals can be taken into account at the expenses of efficiency. They will make the diet more variegated, they will be an insurance against some allergy that persons can develop against specific plants, which could lead to the impossibility of having a complete diet, and, last but not the least, they will contribute very positively to the psychological life of the crew. Animals are already used in hospitals to alleviate the stress of people undergoing certain medical treatment, especially children, and to mitigate serious men-

tal health issues, like depression, schizophrenia, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and others: the Animal-Assisted Therapy (AAT, sometimes also informally called “Pet Therapy”) is nowadays recognised as a proficient and counter-indication-free medicine for some mental health problems [38, 39, 40]. So some small, vegetarian, edible animals are to be envisaged in such a trip, for example rabbits, chickens, small goats, little fish; their impact could also be substantially reduced by feeding them with the non-edible parts of the plants and vegetables cultivated on board, and by eating their products (eggs, milk) before and instead of just eating their meat. Note that the animals shall not be (necessarily) slaughtered and eaten by their owners, to avoid psychological shocks: even though this has been a common procedure for almost all history of humanity, in a confined environment the bond towards the animal can become greater; on the other hand, maybe the animals would not even be bounded to a single entity inside the spaceship, but owned by a professional and shared between the community: this would still keep the benefits, but avoid any unnecessary complication due to the killing of the animals.

While up to now, to us westerners, eating insects can still seem an awkward and probably disgusting practice, it would be a good idea to integrate them in the food chain of our spaceship⁷ [41, 42]. In all other parts of the world insects are a common food since millennia, and sometimes it constitutes one of the major intake of proteins for the population, particularly the less wealthy part: in fact, insects have one of the highest concentration of proteins of any food on the planets, reaching levels as high as 60% [43] (for comparison, beef, pork and chicken meat stops around 25-28%). Moreover, insects have a good protein conversion efficiency, way higher than mammals, so they represent a very sustainable integration of the space colonists’ diet. The possibilities of usage are actually being experimented heavily just in the last years, for example with the creation of insects flours to be used as integrators in cereals flours in order to enhance their protein content, or as a starting point for animal feed.

Animals and insects could be also an advantage in case of a planet colonisation because they would provide a mean to create a real self-sustaining environment (even tough, making it balanced would be another kettle of fish).

⁷Bees should be foreseen in any case, for pollinating purposes.

5 The Bigger Picture

Technically, when we speak about “life support”, we always mean the very basic elements that are necessary for the human life: oxygen, water, food. This is the case because, for the short space missions humanity has undergone until now (i.e. maximum one-year length), these are the mayor concerns⁸: but in the case of perpetual sustainability, everything has to be taken into account for effectively sustain the crew alive. Medicine factories have to be envisaged on board (clearly would be impossible to store medicines for all the possible diseases for the entirety of crew, for the time necessary for the travel; moreover, new diseases, like new strains of bacteria, could develop during the travel, for which the development of new drugs would become essential), together with a variety of way of keeping the people healthy, spanning from gyms to pools to a lot of kind of different sports fields and equipment. The mental health of the crew is also of foremost importance, so aggregation places and leisure venues have to be properly planned, like theatres, cinemas, bars, clubs, restaurants, spa, etc. It is also known that the prolonged abstinence from nature can easily generate depression in human beings [44], and this has to be strongly taken into consideration while planning a multi-generational spaceship, since entire generations will spend their entire life inside the vehicle. Green and plants have to be arranged in a way not to be concentrated in single areas, but widespread in all the spaces occupied normally by the crew, in order to be a constant presence; gardens has to be organised, so to give a moment of escape from the coldness and closure of the spaceship. The animals can also be of great help from this point of view, maybe in sorts of zoo-farms in which the colonists could have different level of interactions with the animals.

In a distant future⁹, we can imagine to be able to create a life support system based on a biorefinery: like petroleum is differentiated in distinct molecules in the fractional distillation, this plant would transform the wastes into reusable compounds (ranging from complex molecules like carbohydrates and polymers, to simple one like water, methane and even single elements) and separate them into different containers, ready to be put to use in the most appropriate way.

In a broader sense, the spaceship has to be a mini

⁸Which make sense: mayor health problems can be excluded via astronauts’ selection and issues as vitamins deficiency takes definitely more time to kill a person than lack of oxygen.

⁹But, maybe, not too distant: see, for example, [45]

replication of Earth not only from the ecological point of view, but also from the physical and social structures: in fact, while it is entirely possible that new society models will be developed specifically for interstellar ship, it is also very unlikely that such an important and delicate mission will be used as a test case for new human social contracts. In any case, the entire chain of knowledge has to be maintained, spanning from the elementary school to the university, with a strong research attitude; while not exempt from flaws, democracy seems to be the government model which keeps the longer stability and ensure the rights of the most: so the three powers (legislative, executive and judicial) are very likely to be present, together with a lot of independent organisms, in order to maintain peace an order in the community. While everybody would probably be happy without, I do not think the administrative machine could be left on ground by the departing pioneers. Clearly, the spaceship shall have the means of producing all the objects necessary, included all the parts of the spaceship itself (from that point of view, it has to be a von Neumann self-replicating machine, if we include humans in the loop): current and foreseen advancement in 3D printing and nanotechnology could make this job a lot easier.

Another topic, which should deserve an article by itself, is radiation. Radiation is widely known to be ones of the mayor problem of space travel: is very harmful both to humans and to equipment, is ubiquitous and hard to shield against it. While the understanding of the physics behind it is well understood, an effective way of protecting the spacecraft from it is still researched.

The radiation in space inside the Solar System can be divided in two categories: the solar radiation and the Galactic Cosmic Rays (GCR) [46]. The solar radiation is composed of protons, electrons, higher Z^{10} nuclei (like He, C, etc.) and electromagnetic (EM) radiation¹¹, emitted radially from our star continuously. The emission, though, is not constant: the Sun undergoes an 11-year cycle where its emissions flux oscillates, and during the most active part of the cycle solar flares can happens. These are extremely powerful, random events where an eruption take place on the surface of the Sun, called coronal mass ejection; this triggers an extreme

emission of particle and EM radiation that could potentially kill astronauts in minutes, if not shielded. Solar flares are probably the biggest radiation problem inside the Solar System, mainly because of its aleatority [47]. On the other hand, GCR is the sum of all the radiation coming from outside of the Solar System [48]: it is mainly composed of protons, electrons and EM waves, it is omnidirectional and it spans a huge range of different energies (the extreme energetic cosmic rays arrive above 10^{20} eV! [49]).

We, on planet Earth, suffer very little from radiation because we are protected from it. In fact, the Earth have a double shield against space radiation: first, the Earth magnetic field deviate charge particles travelling towards it, and bend their trajectory trapping part of the protons and electrons of the Sun into the Van Allen belts [50]. This mechanism actually forms a charged shield that increases the capability of the magnetic field to deflect radiation away from the planet. The second shield is the atmosphere: the radiation that manages to pass through the Van Allen belts has to pass across the atmosphere, where it starts to lose energy by exciting and/or ionising the air molecules. Thanks to this double shielding, the radiation arriving from space on the Earth surface is very low: indeed, this is one of the main reasons why life has flourished on our planet.

A spacecraft, instead, will not have this two natural protections¹², so it will have to provide it by itself. Unluckily, the effective shielding against high energetic EM radiation is material with a high Z, which instead is detrimental against shielding high-energy nucleons, because it will produce a lot of secondary radiation. In fact, if, for example, cosmic radiation passes through lead, it could hit an atom and split it into a spray of several high energy nucleons and/or it can perform electron-positron pair-production while decelerating due to the bremsstrahlung¹³ (an effect called “particle shower”): all this is called secondary radiation, which sometimes is much more harmful that the original incident particle. As a matter of fact, a very high-energy particle will pass through materials (including

¹²The ISS, for example, lacks the protection of the atmosphere, but it is still inside the Van Allen belt: its radiation environment is, therefore, not negligible but also not as substantial as the one in the outer space.

¹³With bremsstrahlung is indicated the electromagnetic radiation produced by the deceleration of a charged particle when deflected by another charged particle, typically an electron by an atomic nucleus. The moving particle loses kinetic energy, which is converted into radiation (i.e., a photon), thus satisfying the law of conservation of energy.

¹⁰In nuclear physics, with Z is indicated the atomic number, which is the total number of protons in the nucleus of an atom, and characterise the element itself; the total number of neutrons, instead, is indicated with N, and their sum is the atomic mass A.

¹¹Which comprehends also the visible light that we enjoy every day from Earth.

the human body) releasing little energy, so it is less dangerous than a medium-energy particle; therefore, a particle shower is absolutely to avoid¹⁴, because it transforms a less harmful radiation in a plethora of highly destructive particles. That is why hydrogen is preferred as shield: not because it blocks radiation better, but because it minimizes secondary radiation. Indeed, since the hydrogen nucleus is only a single proton, it cannot split upon impact, and having the same mass of the incident particle, it maximise the energy absorption. Water, therefore, can be considered as a good trade-off when it comes to radiation shielding: it is not extremely effective as stopping power per thickness, but still it is good, and minimise the production of secondary radiation [46, 51]. So, for our interstellar spaceship, a synergy with the life support system can be envisaged: if all the water tanks and processors are placed all around the hull, they will automatically provide a good shielding to all the systems and the humans inside the vehicle.

A more advanced alternative could be active shielding: one (or more) superconducting magnet could be part of the spacecraft, and generate a magnetic field that would protect the inside similarly to the Van Allen belts of the Earth. This solution, while potentially promising, will be for sure energy consuming, and will place numerous technical challenges; nevertheless, the technology is currently under research [52, 53, 54].

Last, but surely not least, is the power generation: for an interstellar travel, solar power is automatically ruled out, because it would be too little in the space between a star and its neighbour one (already mission in our solar system have problem if the orbit is further than Mars or Jupiter). The ship should then be autonomous in term of power production, carrying on board all the “fuel” necessary: one or more nuclear reactors would be hosted inside, probably fusion one, due to the enormous difference between the energy released by a chemical reaction and a nuclear one. In fact, the ration energy over mass (in MJ/Kg) for burning methane or oil is around 50, while for fusion of deuterium is $\sim 900\,000!$ [55]. Humanity is pretty close to attain viable nuclear fusion power plants, with ITER [56] being the most prominent and ambitious project on the subject: now being built in Cadarache, in the south of France, it is the result of a collaboration of 35 countries in the world, and its aim is to close the gap between the laboratory-scale fusion reactor and a real fusion power plant. Its goal

is to produce more than 500 MW with an input of 50 MW for heating the plasma (so, a ten-fold net power generation).¹⁵

6 A Long Way to Go

As we have shortly seen in this article, succeeding in becoming a space-faring civilization will require several efforts in pushing the boundaries of almost all the human disciplines, from fundamental physics to mass sociology, from computer science to space law. The spaceship for interstellar travel will be a piece of art of engineering, fulfilling its goals by carefully maintaining many delicate equilibria balanced: the life support system would be, for sure, one of the most challenging.

Probably, today, most of the people would smile if asked about interstellar travel, believing it seriously questionable, something relegated forever into the realm of science fiction. Surely it was the same answer Leonardo da Vinci received when proposing his flying machine, and the reaction the spectators of the Wright brothers had when they were trying their first “long jumps”. Nevertheless, when the crew of the first (real!) starship will go on board, they will think back to the dreamer pioneers, and, with a smile, they will begin the greatest adventure of all the times.

References

- [1] Anderson, M.S., Ewert, M.K., Keener, J.F. *et al.* (2015). Life support baseline values and assumptions document. Technical Report TP-2015-218570, NASA. URL <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/archive/nasa/casi.ntrs.nasa.gov/20150002905.pdf>.
- [2] Crusan, J. and Gatens, R. (2017). Cislunar habitation & environmental control & life support systems. In *NASA Advisory Council, Human Exploration and Operations Committee*, pages 1–42. NASA.
- [3] James, J.T. (2008). Spacecraft maximum allowable concentrations for airborne contaminants.

¹⁴Unless it is completely absorbed by the thickness of the shielding, clearly.

¹⁵Theoretically, matter-antimatter for a possible power reactor would have an energy density three order of magnitude greater than deuterium, but the system required to store it and, mostly, the energy necessary to generate the antimatter in first place would hardly be ever convenient over the mass saving, which would be in the order of 100 tons.

- Technical Report JSC-20584, Toxicology Group, NASA. URL <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/archive/nasa/casi.ntrs.nasa.gov/20090014213.pdf>.
- [4] Christgen, M.A. (2005). International Space Station–Medical operations requirements document (ISS MORD). Technical report, NASA. URL emits.sso.esa.int/emits-doc/RD5-ITT-1-5247.pdf. Revision C.
- [5] Muirhead, D., Carter, L., and Williamson, J. (2018). Preventing precipitation in the ISS Urine Processor. Technical report.
- [6] Carter, D.L., Tobias, B., and Orozco, N.Y. (2019). Status of ISS water management and recovery. In *49th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 36.
- [7] Matty, C. (2010). Overview of carbon dioxide control issues during International Space Station/Space Shuttle joint docked operations. In *40th International Conference on Environmental Systems*. ISBN 978-1-60086-957-0. doi:10.2514/6.2010-6251.
- [8] Putz, D. and Olthoff, C. (2016). Assessment of the impacts of ACLS on the ISS life support system using dynamic simulations in V-HAB. In *46th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 170.
- [9] Bockstahler, K., Hartwich, R., and Matthias, C. (2017). Status of the advanced closed loop system ACLS for accommodation on the ISS. In *47th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 135.
- [10] Jones, H. (2006). Comparison on bioregenerative and physico-chemical life support systems. In *SAE Technical Papers*. doi:10.4271/2006-01-2082.
- [11] Massa, G., Wheeler, R., Morrow, C. *et al.* (2016). Growth chambers on the International Space Station for large plants. In *8th International Symposium on Light in Horticulture*, 1134, pages 215–222. doi:10.17660/ActaHortic.2016.1134.29.
- [12] Hanford, A., Anderson, M., Ewert, M. *et al.* (2018). Potential evolution of crop production in space using Veggie. In *48th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 324.
- [13] Morrow, R., C Richter, R., Tellez, G. *et al.* (2016). A new plant habitat facility for the ISS. In *46th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 320.
- [14] Boscheri, G. (2016). PFPU - preliminary concept and main criticalities of the Precursor of Food Production Unit in the MELiSSA framework. In *Agrospace Conference*.
- [15] Hauslage, J., Strauch, S.M., Essmann, O. *et al.* (2018). Eu:CROPIS - *Euglena gracilis*: combined regenerative organic-food production in space - a space experiment testing biological life support systems under lunar and martian gravity. *Microgravity Science and Technology*, **30(6)**:933–942. doi:10.1007/s12217-018-9654-1.
- [16] Kelsey, L., Pasadilla, P., and Cognata, T. (2018). Closing the water loop for exploration: 2018 status of the Brine Processor Assembly. In *48th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*.
- [17] Greenwood, Z. (2018). Plasma methane pyrolysis for spacecraft oxygen loop closure. In *11th International Conference on Plasma Assisted Technologies*. Abu Dhabi, UAE.
- [18] Abney, M.B., Mansell, J.M., Atkins, B. *et al.* (2015). Advanced oxygen recovery via Series-Bosch technology. In *45th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*.
- [19] Sakai, Y. and Nakanoya, S. (2016). An overview of JAXA R&D in regenerative life support systems. Agrospace Conference. URL <https://www.melissafoundation.org/download/24>. Accessed: 2020-03-30.
- [20] Maury-Ramirez, A., editor (2015). *Photocatalytic coatings for air-purifying, self-cleaning and antimicrobial properties*. MDPI AG. ISBN 978-3-03842-137-5.
- [21] Zabel, P., Bamsey, M., Zeidler, C. *et al.* (2017). Future exploration greenhouse design of the EDEN ISS project. In *47th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 95.
- [22] Boscheri, G., Volponi, M., Lamantea, M. *et al.* (2017). Main performance results of the EDEN

- ISS rack-like plant growth facility. In *47th International Conference on Environmental Systems (ICES)*, page 139.
- [23] Salisbury, F.B., Gitelson, J.I., and Lisovsky, G.M. (1997). Bios-3: Siberian experiments in bioregenerative life support. *BioScience*, **47(9)**:575–585. doi:10.2307/1313164.
- [24] Biosphere 2 Official website. URL biosphere2.org. Accessed: 2020-03-30.
- [25] Alling, A. and Nelson, M. (1993). *Life under glass: the inside story of Biosphere 2*. Synergetic Press. ISBN 978-1-88242-807-6.
- [26] Allen, J.P. (2009). *Me and the Biospheres: a memoir by the inventor of Biosphere 2*. Synergetic Press. ISBN 978-0-90779-137-9.
- [27] Poynter, J. (2006). *The human experiment: two years and twenty minutes inside Biosphere 2*. Thunder's Mouth Press. ISBN 978-1-56025-775-2.
- [28] Masuda, T., Ogasawara, T., Harashima, E. *et al.* (2005). Evaluation and implementation of an advanced life support (ALS) menu for closed ecology experiment facilities (CEEF). *Eco-Engineering*, **17(1)**:55–60. doi:10.11450/seitaikogaku.17.55.
- [29] Leyi, H. and Fei, Y. (2014). Chinese scientists prepare for lunar base life support system. *Space Daily*. URL https://www.spacedaily.com/reports/Chinese_scientists_prepare_for_lunar_base_life_support_system_999.html. Accessed: 2020-03-30.
- [30] MacElroy, R., Tremor, J., Smernoff, D. *et al.* (1987). A review of recent activities in the NASA CELSS program. *Advances in Space Research*, **7(4)**:53–57. doi:10.1016/0273-1177(87)90032-9.
- [31] Lasseur, C., Brunet, J., De Weever, H. *et al.* (2010). MELiSSA: the European project of closed life support system. *Gravitational and Space Biology*, **23(2)**.
- [32] Nowicka-Krawczyk, P., Muhlsteniova, R., and Hauer, T. (2019). Detailed characterization of the *Arthrospira* type species separating commercially grown taxa into the new genus *Limnospira* (Cyanobacteria). *Scientific Reports*, **9(1)**:694. doi:10.1038/s41598-018-36831-0.
- [33] Habib, M.A.B., Parvin, M., Huntington, T.C. *et al.* (2008). *Review on culture, production and use of Spirulina as food for humans and feeds for domestic animals and fish*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. ISBN 9789251061060.
- [34] Abdulqader, G., Barsanti, L., and Tredici, M.R. (2000). Harvest of *Arthrospira platensis* from lake Kossorom (Chad) and its household usage among the Kanembu. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, **12(3)**:493–498. doi:10.1023/A:1008177925799.
- [35] Carrington, D. (2002). “Magic number” for space pioneers calculated. *NewScientist*. URL <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn1936-magic-number-for-space-pioneers-calculated/#>. Accessed: 2020-03-30.
- [36] Smith, C.M. (2014). Estimation of a genetically viable population for multigenerational interstellar voyaging: review and data for project Hyperion. *Acta Astronautica*, **97**:16–29. ISSN 0094-5765. doi:10.1016/j.actaastro.2013.12.013.
- [37] Chouker, A., Bereiter-Hahn, J., Singer, D. *et al.* (2019). Hibernating astronauts - science or fiction? *Pflugers Archiv - European Journal of Physiology*, **471(6)**:819–828. doi:10.1007/s00424-018-2244-7.
- [38] Maujean, A., Pepping, C., and Kendall, E. (2015). A systematic review of randomized controlled trials of animal-assisted therapy on psychosocial outcomes. *Anthrozoos*, **28(1)**:23–36. doi:10.2752/089279315X14129350721812.
- [39] Goddard, A.T. and Gilmer, M.J. (2015). The role and impact of animals with pediatric patients. *Pediatric nursing*, **41(2)**:65–71.
- [40] Hoagwood, K., Acri, M., Morrissey, M. *et al.* (2016). Animal-assisted therapies for youth with or at risk for mental health problems: a systematic review. *Applied Developmental Science*, **21(1)**:1–13. doi:10.1080/10888691.2015.1134267.
- [41] Yi, L. (2015). *A study on the potential of insect protein and lipid as a food source*. PhD thesis, Wageningen University, the Netherlands.

- [42] M Salter, A. (2019). Insect protein: a sustainable and healthy alternative to animal protein? *The Journal of Nutrition*, **149(4)**:545–546. doi: 10.1093/jn/nxy315.
- [43] Bukkens, S.G.F. (1997). The nutritional value of edible insects. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition*, **36(2-4)**:287–319. doi:10.1080/03670244.1997.9991521.
- [44] Seymour, V. (2016). The human–nature relationship and its impact on health: a critical review. *Frontiers in Public Health*, **4**:260. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2016.00260.
- [45] Pauli, G. (2017). *The Blue Economy 3.0: The marriage of science, innovation and entrepreneurship creates a new business model that transforms society*. Xlibris AU. ISBN 978-1524521073.
- [46] Simonsen, L.C. and Nealy, J.E. (1991). Radiation protection for human missions to the Moon and Mars. Technical Report NASA-TP-3079, NASA. URL <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=19910008686>.
- [47] Jonas, F.M. (2015). *Handbook of cosmic hazards and planetary defense*, chapter Solar Flares, pages 37–46. Springer. ISBN 978-3-319-03951-0. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-03952-7_3.
- [48] Shinn, J.L., Nealy, J.E., Townsend, L.W. *et al.* (1994). Galactic Cosmic Ray radiation levels in spacecraft on interplanetary missions. *Advanced Space Research*, **14(10)**:863–871. doi:10.1016/0273-1177(94)90551-7.
- [49] The Pierre Auger Collaboration, Aab, A., Abreu, P. *et al.* (2017). Observation of a large-scale anisotropy in the arrival directions of cosmic rays above 8×10^{18} eV. *Science*, **357**:1266–1270. doi: 10.1126/science.aan4338.
- [50] Murdin, P., editor (2000). *Encyclopedia of Astronomy and Astrophysics*, chapter Van Allen Belts, page 4417. CRC Press. ISBN 978-0750304405. doi:10.1888/0333750888/4417.
- [51] Wilson, J.W., Miller, J., Konradi, A. *et al.* (1997). Shielding strategies for human space exploration. Technical Report NASA-CP-3360, NASA. URL <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=19980137598>.
- [52] Sussingham, J.C., Watkins, S.A., and Cocks, F.H. (1999). Forty years of development of active systems for radiation protection of spacecraft. *The Journal of Astronautical Sciences*, **47(3-4)**:165–175.
- [53] Rossi, L., Sorbi, M., and Spillantini, P. (2004). A superconducting magnetic lens for solar rays protection in manned interplanetary missions. In *IEEE Transaction on Applied Superconductivity*, volume 14, pages 1696–1699. doi:10.1109/TASC.2004.831041.
- [54] Musenich, R. and Calvelli, V., Farinon, S., Burger, J. *et al.* (2014). Space radiation superconducting shields. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, volume 507, page 032033. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/507/3/032033.
- [55] Huba, J.D. (2016). NRL (Naval Research Laboratory) plasma formulary. Technical Report NRL/PU/6790-16-614, Naval Research Lab Washington DC Plasma Physics Div.
- [56] ITER Official Website. URL www.iter.org. Accessed: 2020-03-30.
